

Percentage of RTBV (B) and RTSV (S) infection^a as detected by ELISA on test lines and varieties at 30 and 60 DAT, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, and Midsayap, North Cotabato, 3 cropping seasons, 1996-97.

Location/test entry	1996 WS						1997 DS						1997 WS					
	30 DAT			60 DAT			30 DAT			60 DAT			30 DAT			60 DAT		
	B+S	B	S	B+S	B	S	B+S	B	S	B+S	B	S	B+S	B	S	B+S	B	S
<i>Muñoz, Nueva Ecija</i>																		
IR26				4 a	25 c	8 a				0 a	0 a	1 a	0 a	1 a	2 a	0 a	11 b	2 a
TKM6				3 a	15 b	6 a				0 a	0 a	15 a	0 a	3 a	1 a	2 a	11 b	4 a
Utri Merah		No		3 a	9 ab	25 ab		No		0 a	0 a	1 a	0 a	1 a	0 a	0 a	14 b	0 a
IR69705-1-1-3-2-1		ELISA		0 a	1 a	0 a		ELISA		0 a	0 a	10 a	0 a	0 a	7 ab	0 a	0 a	11 ab
IR69706-1-4-2-5-2-2	x ^b	x	x	x	x	x				0 a	0 a	67 b	0 a	0 a	6 ab	0 a	1 a	25 bc
IR73889-5-1-1-1-1-1-2	x	x	x	x	x	x				0 a	0 a	10 a	0 a	0 a	10 ab	0 a	0 a	81 d
IR1561-228-3-3				30 b	5 ab	43 b				0 a	1 a	12 a	1 a	1 a	13 b	14 a	0 a	72 d
TN1				67 c	6 ab	26 ab				2 a	0 a	58 b	9 b	7 b	38 c	54 b	2 a	39 c
<i>Midsayap, North Cotabato</i>																		
IR26	17 a	17 a	11 a	-	-	-	0 a	1 a	1 a	81 d	14 ab	3 ab	60 cd	36 d	2 a	93 c	7 a	0 a
TKM6	12 a	13 a	7 ab	-	-	-	0 a	7 a	7 a	54 c	17 ab	14 bc	54 c	25 c	4 a	82 bc	8 a	4 ab
Utri Merah	2 a	14 a	0 a	4	14	7	0 a	3 a	0 a	3 ab	4 a	17 cd	7 a	11 b	3 a	12 a	10 a	2 a
IR69705-1-1-3-2-1	0 a	8 a	0 a	1	7	3	0 a	2 a	0 a	1 a	0 a	1 a	1 a	10 ab	2 a	1 a	7 a	1 a
IR69706-1-4-2-5-2-2	x	x	x	x	x	x	2 a	4 a	2 a	1 a	6 a	6 abc	0 a	4 ab	4 a	4 a	13 a	9 b
IR73889-5-1-1-1-1-1-2	x	x	x	x	x	x	1 a	0 a	1 a	13 b	6 a	27 d	35 b	0 a	41 b	79 b	17 a	0 a
IR1561-228-3-3	- ^c	-	-	-	-	-	1 a	3 a	4 a	43 c	27 b	7 abc	68 d	26 c	3 a	87 bc	12 a	0 a
TN1	47 ^d b	7 a	40 b	-	-	-	2 a	1 a	39 b	88 d	9 a	1 a	87 e	2 a	4 a	90 bc	10 a	0 a

^aFrom 123 to 180 plants test entry¹ season¹. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P = 0.05$, Duncan's multiple range test). ^bNot included in the 1996 WS trial. ^cPlants severely damaged by Malayan black bug. ^dSamples include IR1561-228-3-3.

grown in an area with low tungro pressure. The yield of all test entries in North Cotabato was drastically reduced by rice black bug infestation. In the 1997 DS trial, IR69705-1-1-3-2-1

and IR69706-1-4-2-5-2-2 yielded an average of 1.9 and 0.9 t ha⁻¹, respectively. The latter was significantly higher than the 0.7 t ha⁻¹ yield of IR26. The low tungro virus infection and the

relatively high yield of these advanced lines showed their potential use as stop-gap planting materials for tungro disease management. ■

Stress tolerance — excess water

Inheritance of submergence tolerance at the early seedling stage in rainfed lowland rice

B. Swain, B. Acharya, K. Pande, and R.N. De, Central Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Station, IIT Campus, Kharagpur 721302, West Bengal, India

In the early seedling stage, mostly under direct-seeded conditions, lowland rice varieties are subjected to submergence because of erratic rainfall distribution and prolonged water stagnation. As a result, crop establishment is poor and productivity is low. Tolerance for submergence is therefore a highly desired trait of rainfed lowland varieties.

We studied the inheritance of submergence tolerance in four crosses

Segregation ratio for submergence tolerance in F₂ generation of different crosses.

Cross	Submergence score		Seedlings in F ₂ (no.)		χ^2	Ratio	Probability
	Parents	F ₁	T ^a	S			
FR43B (T)/ IR42(S)	2.6 (T) 8.5 (S)	4.0 (T)	151	104	0.911	9:7	0.5-0.3
FR43B (T)/ Pankaj (S)	2.6 (T) 9.0 (S)	4.2 (T)	147	108	0.201	9:7	0.7-0.5
Rahaspanjar (T) IR42 (S)	3.6 (T) 8.5 (S)	4.5 (T)	140	115	0.187	9:7	0.7-0.5
Rahaspanjar (T) Pankaj (S)	3.6 (T) 8.8 (S)	4.9 (T)	142	113	0.033	9:7	0.9-0.8

^aT = tolerant, S = susceptible.

involving two tolerant (T) varieties—FR43B and Rahaspanjar—and two susceptible (S) varieties—IR42 and Pankaj. Seeds of parents, F₁s, and F₂s of each cross were raised in galvanized-iron trays (70 × 60 × 15 cm) filled with clay soil on polythene sheet. Twenty

lines with 15 seedlings line⁻¹ were grown in each tray. Both parents and their F₁s were grown in a single line each, whereas the rest of the populations were raised in RCBD with three replications.

Thirty-five-day-old seedlings were completely submerged in an artificial

cemented tank. A water depth of 50 cm above the seedling level and a water temperature of 30 °C were maintained for 12 d. Recovery score was measured 7 d after submergence (1-5, tolerant; >5-9, susceptible).

ANOVA revealed significant differences among the populations in reaction to submergence.

Submergence scores in the F₁s of four crosses-FR43B(T)/IR42(S), FR43B(T)/Pankaj(S), Rahaspanjar(T)/IR42(S), and Rahaspanjar(T)/

Pankaj(S)-tended toward those of the tolerant parents.

In the F₂ generation, the segregation ratio was 9:7 (T:S) (see table). This ratio indicated that submergence tolerance can be explained by the complementary action of at least two genes. ■

Stress tolerance — adverse soils

Performance of different rice lines in Zn-deficient soil

P. Thongbai, G.J.D. Kirk, C. Quijano, and D. Senadhira, IRRI

Ten rice lines with different responses to Zn deficiency were grown in a Zn-deficient soil with 0 (Zn0) or 10 (Zn10) mg Zn kg⁻¹ soil. The soil was a fine montmorillonitic calcareous Typic Hydraquent from Tiaong, Quezon, Philippines (DTPA-extractable Zn 0.04 mg kg⁻¹, pH 7.8). Portions (3 kg) of the

soil were placed in plastic pots and flooded with water for 3 wk. Pre-germinated seeds were then sown and the plants were grown for 3 wk in a glasshouse under typical humid tropical wet-season conditions. The following measurements were made: Zn deficiency score by the IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice*, number of leaves with Zn deficiency symptoms, number of tillers, plant height, shoot dry weight, and shoot Zn content.

Nine indices of performance were calculated from the results and ranked (Table 1). These indices are all quantitative and Zn-specific, and could therefore be used for quantitative trait loci (QTL) analysis. The indices were used to distinguish different performance characteristics (Table 2).

Results showed that lines IR26, IR58, CSR10, and IR65 were intolerant of Zn deficiency, with IR26, CSR10, and IR65 tending to accumulate Zn without an increase in growth. Lines IR8192, Madhukar, FR13A, Ketumbar, and to a

Table 1. Performance indices for growth under Zn deficiency.

Performance index	Scoring	Ranking ^a											
		IR26	IR58	IR65	CSR10	Ketumbar	KDML 105	IR9764	Mahsuri	FR 13 A	IR8192	Kuatik Putih	Madhukar
Visual score in Zn0	a: best, d: worst	d	c	b	b	a	c	a	c	a	a	c	a
Number of leaves with deficiency symptoms in Zn0	a: least, d: most	d	c	b	b	b	c	a	d	d	a	d	d
Shoot dry wt/shoot Zn concentration in Zn0	a: highest, c: lowest	c	b	c	b	b	b	b	c	a	a	c	b
Shoot dry wt/ quantity of Zn in shoot in Zn0	a: highest, g: lowest	f	b	g	e	b	b	c	f	b	a	d	c
Shoot Zn concentration in Zn0	a: highest, e: lowest	a	e	a	b	e	c	b	a	e	e	b	d
Quantity of Zn in shoot in Zn0	a: highest, c: lowest	c	c	c	c	c	b	b	c	a	a	c	a
Av % growth (dry wt, tiller no.) reduction	a: least, d: most	c	d	d	c	b	b	b	b	b	a	a	a
(Dry wt Zn0/dry wt Zn10)%	a: highest, d: lowest	c	c	b	d	c	a	b	d	a	a	d	a
(Dry wt Zn10 - dry wt Zn0)/quantity of Zn supplied	a: highest, g: lowest	f	e	g	b	d	f	c	a	b	a	b	b

^aThe same letters in a row indicate that rankings are not significantly different at *P* = 0.05 by Duncan's multiple range test.

Table 2. Performance characteristics based on indices in Table 1.

Characteristic	Index rankings required	IR26	IR58	IR65	CSR10	Ketumbar	KDML 105	IR9764	Mahsuri	FR13A	IR8192	Kuatik Putih	Madhukar
Tolerance deficiency	Low 1, 2, 7	L ^a	L	ML	ML	H	MH	H	MH	MH	H	MH	H
Internal efficiency (transport and use within plant)	High 3, 4, 6; low 5	-	-	-	-	H	M	L	L	H	H	L	H
External efficiency (mobilization in rhizosphere, absorption)	Low 3, 4, 6; high 5	-	-	-	-	L	M	H	H	L	L	H	L
Responsiveness	High 8, 9	L	M	L	MH	M	L	M	MH	H	HH	MH	H
High accumulation (high shoot Zn with poor growth)	High 5, low 6	H	L	H	H	L	M	H	H	L	L	H	L
Low accumulation (low shoot Zn with good growth)	Low 5, high 6	L	MH	L	L	M	M	ML	L	HH	HH	L	H

^aH = high, M = moderate, L = low.